

Extraction of titanium and molybdenum with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene and their sequential determination in silicate rocks, ores, minerals, concentrates and steel samples by molecular absorption spectroscopy

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Abstract : A facile liquid-liquid extraction system for titanium and molybdenum using the 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene has been developed. After extractive separation and spectrophotometric determination of titanium in the organic solvent, *n*-butylacetate at pH 4–9, the aqueous solution was used for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum. The molar absorptivity of the Ti-system ($3.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was found to be maximum at 390 nm in *n*-butylacetate. Similarly, the molar absorptivity of the Mo-system ($1.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was found to be maximum, at 400 nm in *n*-butylacetate. Mo(VI) was reduced to Mo(V) using hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Except titanium, which was eliminated by the prior solvent extraction of Ti-2,3-H₂ND complex at pH 4–9 where Mo(VI)-2,3-H₂ND complex was not extracted, no other element was found to interfere seriously in the determination of molybdenum. The method was applied to the determination of titanium and molybdenum in a wide variety of samples like silicate rocks, ores, minerals, concentrates and steel samples.

Keywords : Titanium, molybdenum, liquid-liquid extraction, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene.

Introduction

Molybdenum is an important element. It has got application in metallurgy, agriculture, industries and different biological processes¹. It is used in integrated circuits, anti-friction coatings, catalysts, aircrafts parts, missile parts, high-temperature vacuum components, furnace components, silicon power devices etc.². Molybdenum is also an essential trace element in animal physiology³. Molybdenum is also a path-finder element for sandstone and unconformity related uranium deposits⁴. Owing to its wide applications in different fields, it is often needed to estimate molybdenum content accurately in different materials (artificial and natural).

There are innumerable methods for the determination of molybdenum⁵. A number of spectrophotometric reagents are known for its determination. Although some of the reagents are extremely sensitive but are poor in selectivity i.e. many concomitant ions do interfere. Various methods have been suggested to eliminate their in-

terference by way of the addition of masking agents or by selective removal of some of these interfering elements by liquid-liquid extraction prior to the actual determination of molybdenum. However, these methods are cumbersome, lengthy and time consuming. Flame-AAS method for molybdenum determination are usually not sensitive, hence not useful for trace determination of molybdenum. ICP-AES is suitable for molybdenum determination, however as observed by us, the results obtained in certain samples are not always satisfactory in terms of precision and accuracy. Therefore, spectrophotometric determinations of molybdenum in most of the samples are the mainstay till date. The well-known thiocyanate methods with innumerable modifications suffer from a number of limiting factors such as variation of absorbance with respect to concentration of Fe, SCN⁻, SnCl₂ and H⁺, instability of colour etc.⁶. As stated above, some of the highly sensitive methods for the spectrophotometric determination of micro amounts of the metal suffer from interference of

Fe, Cu, W etc. The potassium ethyl xanthate method is complicated, V and W interfere, and the absorption of reagent blanks is relatively large. The nitron is the most selective method but the presence of iron is necessary for the complete extraction of the metal. In addition, a longer time (20 min) is required for complete formation of chelate. The 2-mercaptobenzo-*r*-thiopyrone method is also sensitive but suffers from interference of Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, F⁻ or S₂O₃⁻, absorption of reagent at λ_{max} and variation of the intensity of the complex with respect to amount of reagent added. The tetraphenylarsonium chloride is also complicated because, Ti(III) is required for full colour development, and W, Nb and Ni (> 10 fold) interfere.

The reagent, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) has been well documented to react with a number of metal ions such as Fe⁷, Ti^{8,9}, Nb¹⁰, V¹¹, Mo¹², Mn¹³, U¹⁴, Th¹⁵, REEs^{16,17}, etc. to form respective coloured/colourless complexes/chelates suitable for their extractive spectrophotometric/fluorimetric/AAS determination. However, only few reports are available for the studies carried out on the reaction of molybdenum with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene, that too with Mo(VI)¹⁸. While estimating Mo(VI) with this reagent by extractive spectrophotometry, Ti(IV) invariably interferes, entailing a great deal of difficulty in obtaining accurate results for the determination of molybdenum. Therefore, it calls for a separation of titanium from molybdenum in order to selectively estimate the later one.

In the proposed method, a novel technique has been devised by which both Ti and Mo has been separated quantitatively by way of liquid-liquid extraction and individually determined spectrophotometrically. In this technique, first Ti is extracted at pH 4-5 leaving Mo(VI) in aqueous solution. As has already been discussed in our earlier papers⁸ on Ti, Ti(IV) readily forms yellowish-orange neutral complex at pH 4-9, extractable in the solvent ethylacetate, and the molar absorptivity of the system being $3.2 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the present system, Ti is extracted into *n*-butylacetate and the absorption is measured at 390 nm ($\epsilon = 3.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Mo(VI) left in the aqueous solution was reduced with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and the complex of Mo(V) with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) displaying a yellow coloration was readily extracted into *n*-butylacetate,

and its absorbance for molybdenum determination was measured at 400 nm (molar absorptivity being $1.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This way, a method has been developed for sequential and selective determination of Ti and Mo in a host of samples such as rocks, soils, minerals, stream sediments, steel and alloys and molybdenum concentrates. The method has been applied to a host of samples including a set of CRMs, and the results obtained were found to be favourably comparable with those obtained by applying standard methods/with the certified or recommended values.

Experimental

Apparatus :

(a) UV-Vis Spectrophotometer. An analytik jena, Germany, make double beam UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Model : SPECORD-250) was used for absorption measurements. .

(b) An Elico-make pH meter(model LI-120) was used for pH measurements.

(c) Duran make Separating Funnels of 125 mL capacity were used for solvent extraction studies.

Reagents :

All the reagents used were of AR grade.

(a) Solvents : Ethyl/butyl acetate was used for the extraction of the metal complexes.

(b) Reducing agents : Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (NH₂OH.HCl), SnCl₂, ascorbic acid etc. were used for the studies involving reduction of Mo(VI) to Mo(V).

(c) 2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene : Flucka (98% pure) as well as Merck (98% pure) make reagent was used for complex formation/extraction studies.

(d) Acids : HCl, H₂SO₄, HNO₃ and NH₄HF₂ were used for sample decomposition.

(e) Ammonium molybdate and titanium dioxide : Ammonium molybdate heptahydrate and titanium dioxide were used for the preparation of standard reference solutions.

Procedure :

Dissolution of silicate rocks, ores, minerals, soils and stream sediments :

A weighed quantity (0.5 g) of finely crushed sample material (~200 mesh), 3 g of solid extrapure NH₄HF₂

and 10 mL of 1 : 1 H₂SO₄ were taken into a clean (125 mL capacity) Teflon beaker. The beaker was covered with a Teflon lid and heated on a hot plate at 200 °C for around one hour. Repeated the above process if any residue was left/unattacked. The lid of the beaker was then removed and the content of the beaker was heated on the hot plate till the copious fume (aerosol) of SO₃ ceased to appear. Added about 2–3 mL of conc. HNO₃ and about 30 mL of water and digested the mixture for 20–30 min. The Teflon beaker was then removed and allowed to cool to room temperature. The contents of the beaker were transferred to a 100 mL PFA volumetric (plastic) flask and made up the volume to the mark.

Dissolution of steel samples :

A 0.2 g of steel sample was taken in a 250 mL beaker. Added 10 mL of 1 : 1 HNO₃ and heated it onto a hot plate till it goes into solution. Neutralized the solution and the pH of the solution should be ~3–4, and then made up the volume to 100 mL in a volumetric flask.

Extraction of metals and their absorption measurements :

(a) Extraction and determination of titanium :

A 5 mL of aliquot depending on the content of titanium was taken into a 125 mL separating funnel. To it was taken 0.1 g solid 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene and mixed well. Then added 10 mL of 10% sodium acetate and the pH was adjusted to 4–5. Added 10 mL of *n*-butylacetate and shaken for 3 min. Ti and Fe passed into the organic solvent as their respective neutral complexes. Allowed for phase separation and the aqueous layer was drained out and stored for molybdenum determination. Titanium was separated from Fe by adding ~10 mL water and shaking the separating funnel for a while (~1 min) after raising the pH to 8.0–10 by adding few drops of ammonia. This way, iron passed into aqueous solution as its red anionic complex formed with this very reagent, leaving Ti-2,3-H₂ND neutral complex in *n*-butylacetate. A portion of the entrapped iron complex in organic solvent was scrubbed with distilled water, thereby completely separating Ti from iron. Measured the absorbance of the yellowish orange colour of the Ti(IV)-2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene in butylacetate against a reagent blank prepared in the same fashion at 390 nm.

(b) Extraction and determination of molybdenum :

To the aqueous solution obtained from the extraction of Ti and contained in a 125 mL separating funnel, added 5 mL of 20% NH₂OH-HCl. Mixed well and set it aside for 5 min. Then added 0.5 g solid 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene and mixed well. Adjusted the pH to 2–4 and then added 10 mL of *n*-butylacetate. Shaken the mixture of about 3 min and allowed for phase separation. Discarded the aqueous layer and then measured the absorbance of the organic phase containing the Mo-2,3-H₂ND neutral complex at 400 nm against the reagent blank prepared similarly without containing any molybdenum.

Results and discussion

It is well known that spectrophotometric methods for the determination of Ti and Mo are the mainstay because of having an edge over AAS methods in terms of its sensitivity of determination. AAS determinations of both Ti and Mo are not satisfactory because of sensitivity constraints. The reagent, 2,3-H₂ND has been reported to form complexes with a host of elements such as Ti, Mn, V, Nb, Fe, U, Th, REEs *etc.* Analytical potential of most of these complexes have been tapped/made use of in the spectrophotometric determination of these elements in silicate rocks and allied products. In order to determine them accurately, their selective separation from each other are often resorted to by way of liquid-liquid extraction.

In this paper, an useful method has been reported for the selective and sequential determination of molybdenum and titanium free from interferences of iron and other associated elements. Titanium was extracted as neutral complex of this reagent, [2,3-H₂ND] at pH 4–5 into *n*-butylacetate leaving molybdenum(VI) in aqueous solution. The aqueous solution was separated and stored for the determination of molybdenum. Titanium was separated from Fe by re-extracting these two complexes contained in the organic solvent at pH 8–10, whereby iron passed into aqueous solution as its anionic complex with this very reagent, leaving Ti-2,3-H₂ND neutral complex in *n*-butylacetate. A portion of the entrapped iron complex in organic solvent was scrubbed with distilled water thereby completely separating Ti from iron. Ti free from iron and other associated elements was selectively determined by measuring the absorption of Ti-2,3-H₂ND complex at 390 nm (its λ_{\max}). Similarly, Mo(VI) left in the

aqueous phase of the first extraction was reduced to Mo(v) by hydroxylamine hydrochloride and then readily extracted as its neutral complex with 2,3-H₂ND into *n*-butylacetate at pH 2–4. The absorbance of the yellowish orange complex was measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank.

For the following studies, a 25 µg of Ti/Mo was taken per 25 mL of *n*-butylacetate.

Absorption spectra :

The absorption spectra of Ti-2,3-H₂ND complex and the reagent blank have already been studied and reported⁸ and in this work, further study on this aspect is not necessary. Spectra of Mo complex with 2,3-H₂ND and the corresponding reagent blank are shown in Fig. 1. While the Ti-2,3-H₂ND complex absorbs maximum at 390 nm, the corresponding absorption maxima for the Mo complex was found to be at 400 nm. The absorption of reagent blanks for both the above system were in the range 0.0010 to 0.0025.

Effect of reducing agent on the reduction of Mo(vi) :

As stated in the preceding section, Mo(v)-2,3-H₂ND is easily extractable in ethyl/butyl acetate and Mo(vi) complex with the same reagent is not extractable in these solvents. Therefore, Mo(vi) was reduced to Mo(v) using hydroxylamine hydrochloride. A 5 mL of 20% (m/v) NH₂OH-HCl was found to be effective in reducing Mo(vi), as is evident by maximum molar absorptivity of the extracted complex ($1.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Other reducing agent like SnCl₂, ascorbic acid was also tried. However hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave the most desired

result. Fig. 2 shows the results.

Effect of reagent (2,3-H₂ND) concentration :

This aspect was well studied in our earlier work^{8,9}, and further studies on this fact are redundant. Similarly, for obtaining maximum absorbance in case of Mo, a 0.8 g of the reagent per 20 mL of *n*-butylacetate was recommended for maximum sensitivity. Fig. 3 shows the effect of 2,3-H₂ND on the extraction of molybdenum(v).

Effect of pH on the formation and extraction of Ti and Mo complexes :

Ti(IV) forms a 1 : 3 neutral complex in the pH range 4–9. This aspect was well established in our earlier publication. Further studies on this aspect are redundant. This complex is readily extractable in a suitable solvent like ethylacetate or *n*-butylacetate. However 1 : 2 Mo(v)-2,3-H₂ND complex is formed at pH 2–4, and at this very pH range, the yellowish orange Mo-chelate is extracted in ethyl or butyl acetate. Fig. 4 shows the effect of pH on the extraction of molybdenum(v).

Effect of solvents on the extraction of Ti and Mo complexes with 2,3-H₂ND :

Many solvents like benzene, toluene, xylene, butanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ethylacetate, butylacetate and MIBK were tried for the extraction of Ti and Mo complexes formed. In the present study, *n*-butylacetate gave the most satisfactory results in terms of ease of extraction and maximum sensitivity of spectrophotometric determinations.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of molybdenum complex and reagent blank against butyl acetate; (a) complex vs reagent blank (Mo, 20 µg per 20 mL); (b) reagent blank vs butylacetate.

Fig. 2. Effect of reducing agent (hydroxylamine hydrochloride) on the extraction of 10 μg Mo(V) into 10 mL of *n*-butylacetate [0.8 g 2,3-H₂ND; 5 mL of 20% (m/v) NH₂OH.HCl; pH 2-4].

Fig. 3. Effect of complexing agent (2,3-H₂ND) concentration on the colour intensity of the molybdenum complex (Mo, 20 μg per 20 mL).

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, detection limit, determination limit and precision of the method :

The molar absorptivity of Ti-2,3-H₂ND present system is around $3.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Beer's law for the Ti-2,3-H₂ND system obeyed in the range 0 to 5

$\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The detection and determination limits of Ti were 0.03 and 0.08 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively. Similarly, Beer's law for Mo(V)-2,3-H₂ND system was obeyed in the range, 0.01 to 6 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The detection and determination limits of Mo were 0.06 and 0.20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respec-

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on the extraction of 20 µg Mo(V) into 20 mL of *n*-butylacetate [0.8 g 2,3-H₂ND; 5 mL of 20% (m/v) NH₂OH.HCl].

tively. The limit of detection defined as $C_L = 3.30 \times S_B/m$, where S_B and m denotes standard deviation of the blank signal and slope of the calibration plot, respectively. Similarly, the limit of determination was defined as $C_L = Y_B + 10 \times S_B$, where Y_B denotes the signal of the blank sample. The precision of determination of 1 µg/mL each of Ti and Mo were 2.5 and 3.0%, respectively.

Effect of electrolyte, time, temperature, volume ratio and standing time :

While the equilibrium period for complete extraction of Ti in *n*-butylacetate as Ti-2,3-H₂ND complex was examined and found to be less than 1 min, the one for Mo-2,3-H₂ND system was about 1 min. In both the cases, the colour intensity of the complex was not affected by the addition of electrolytes such as LiCl, NaCl, KCl, NH₄Cl, (NH₄)₂SO₄, CH₃COONa, KCl, etc. The nature of both the complexes found in solution is not affected by the variation of temperature from 20 to 40 °C and volume of aqueous phase from 5 to 50 mL. The complexes are stable for at least 24 h.

Extraction equilibria and composition of complexes :

(a) *For titanium system :*

The equilibrium studies for Ti-2,3-H₂ND system were already studied and reported in our earlier paper⁹. It has already been established that titanium forms a 1 : 3 complex with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene.

(b) *For molybdenum system :*

The mechanism with which Mo⁵⁺ ion was extracted

from aqueous solution into *n*-butylacetate by the same reagent (2,3-H₂ND) follows the reaction as given below.

After reduction of Mo(VI) with NH₂OH.HCl, the main species which predominantly appears in acidic medium (pH 2 to 4) is a monomer MoO³⁺ 19 which dimerises through a bridging oxygen as (Mo₂O₃)⁴⁺. This species reacts with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (2,3-H₂ND) as follows.

where H₂ND stands for 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene.

The equilibrium constant, β of the reaction can be written as,

$$\beta = \frac{[Mo_2O_3(HND)_w]^{(4-w)}_o \times [H^+]^w}{[Mo_2O_3]^{4+} \times [H_2ND]_o^w} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or, } \beta = \frac{D \times [H^+]^w}{[H_2ND]_o^w} \quad (3)$$

where,

$$D = \frac{[Mo_2O_3(HND)_w]^{(4-w)}_o}{[Mo_2O_3]^{4+}}$$

Eq. (3) can be written as,

$$\log \beta_{(w)} = \log D - wpH - w \log [H_2ND]_o \quad (4)$$

Analysing the experimental values of distribution ratio (D) as a function of equilibrium pH and extractant concentration at constant values of other parameters allows estimation of the number of extractant molecules associated with the extracted metal. The “slope analysis” was made use of in the study of distribution behaviour of Mo(v) by plotting the logarithmic values of distribution ratio of Mo(v) vs experimental variables (curve fitting method)²⁰. From the plot of log D value vs logarithmic concentration of 2,3-H₂ND in the organic phase the slope of 2 was obtained. It showed that two(2) 2,3-H₂ND molecules were used in the extraction process. This result indicates, w = 4. Thus the stoichiometry of the complex is 1 : 2 (Mo : H₂ND). Thus the extracted complex under optimized reaction conditions i.e. pH 2–4 is a neutral complex, [Mo₂O₃(HND)₄] or [MoO₃(C₁₀H₇O₂)₄]. Similar complexes of Mo(v) with ligand like 6-chloro-3-hydroxyl-2-(3 hydroxy phenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran

(CHHB) are, however, not unprecedented²¹.

Tentative structure of the complexes :

- Titanium :

- Molybdenum :

The possible structure of the complex was supported by the IR spectra^{21,22} in which a strong band at 946 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 745 cm^{-1} were assigned to Mo=O absorption and to antisymmetric Mo-O-Mo stretching, respectively.

Effect of diverse ions :

(i) *For titanium estimation :*

Most of the elements like Al, Ba, Ca, Mg, Li, Na, K, and Rb do not interfere at 1000 fold concentration to titanium. U and Th do not interfere upto 100 fold excess to Ti. Co, Ni, Zn, Mn, Se, Sr, Pb, Sb, Bi, Cd and Ag can be tolerated upto 10 fold excess to Ti. W, V, Zr, Cr(III) do not interfere upto 3 fold excess to Ti. However, Cr(VI) which interferes seriously in aqueous system, does not interfere when Ti is extracted into *n*-butylacetate. Similarly, a 1000 fold excess of anions like I^- , Cl^- , acetate, NO_3^- and 50 fold excess to SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , IO_3^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ and CO_3^{2-} do not interfere. However, F^- interferes at 5 fold excess to Ti.

(ii) *For molybdenum estimation :*

In molybdenum estimation, the interfering effect of a host of ions which are present in rocks, soils, and sediment samples have been studied. The interference of Ti in Mo determination and vice-versa have been well taken care of during solvent extraction of the respective elements. As stated previously, while extracting Ti, Mo(VI) which is not extractable at optimized condition for Ti extraction, is automatically eliminated in the case of Ti determination, and at the same time while extracting Mo(V) after reduction of Mo(VI), Ti does not interfere because it

is already extracted out. Iron in this particular case, does not interfere because along with Ti, Fe also gets extracted, and thus eliminated. Moreover, any residual iron if at all left in the aqueous phase, while extracting Ti is reduced to ferrous state during reduction of Mo(VI) to Mo(V), which is not extracted along with Mo. Hence, iron does not interfere in the estimation of Mo. Elements like V, Cu, Nb are also eliminated during the extraction of Ti and as such do not interfere in the determination of Mo. Mn also does not interfere in the determination of Mo because it is not extracted along with Mo.

The tolerance limit of different cations and anions present in the samples studied are given in parentheses. For the determination of 10 μg Mo per 10 mL, 10,000 μg of the following ions are tolerated with less than 2% error. The ions are Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , U^{6+} , Rb, Sr, Ba, Zr, Th, Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SO_4^{2-} , acetate and citrate. Similarly for the determination of same amount of Mo as mentioned above, a 100 μg of the following ions are tolerated for less than 2% error. The ions are Cr^{3+} and Cr^{6+} , Ce^{3+} and Ce^{4+} , W^{6+} , Sn^{4+} , Sn^{2+} , Ge^{4+} etc.

Analytical application :

The method was thoroughly applied to a host of samples of diverse matrices such as rocks, soils, stream sediments, minerals and steel and alloys for the sequential determination of both the metal ions, Ti and Mo.

In order to validate the method, it was applied to a few CRMs and the results obtained have been found to be favourably comparable with the certified/recommended values of these elements. The results are shown in Table 1.

Conclusions

The mutual interference of Ti and Mo in their determination by some of the reported methods, including the ones reported earlier by the authors, renders the methods ineffective in yielding correct results. However the present method is highly useful for rapid and sequential determination of Ti and molybdenum in geological and industrial products, particularly when these two metals are present together, in terms of accuracy, precision and ease of operation. Based upon the results obtained for a host of samples of diverse matrices, the method is recommended for the rapid sequential determination of Ti and Mo in the type of samples cited above.

Table 1. Determination of TiO₂ and Mo in different samples

Sl. no.	Sample no./ Nature of samples	TiO ₂ determined by the proposed method (μg g ⁻¹)	Mo estimated by the proposed method (μg g ⁻¹)	TiO ₂ determined by TIRON method (μg g ⁻¹)	Mo determined by the Flame-AAS method (μg g ⁻¹)	Certified value for TiO ₂ (μg g ⁻¹)	Certified value for MO (μg g ⁻¹)
1.	SY-3	1320	10	1350	<50	1300	6.64
2.	MRG-1	42500	15	42900	<50	42700	15
3.	J-991	417	580	430	570	-	-
4.	J-993	410	355	425	349	-	-
5.	J-1000	733	230	759	215	-	-
6.	J-1001	899	125	910	115	-	-
7.	J-1003	914	45	920	<50	-	-
8.	J-1008	760	40	800	<50	-	-
9.	BCS/SS No. 407/1. (Low alloy steel)	-	7750	-	7900	-	-
10.	Molybdenum concentrate	-	42%	-	42.1%	-	-

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References

- F. A. Cotton, G. Wilkinson, C. A. Murrillo and M. Bochman, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 6th ed., Wiley Interscience, New York, USA, 1999.
- V. Srilalitha, A. Raghavendra Guru Prasad, K. Raman Kumar, V. Sheshagiri and K. K. Ravindranath, *Chemical Bulletin of Politechnica, University of Timiscara, Romania*, 2010, **55**, 2.
- E. J. Underwood, "Trace Elements in Human and Animal Nutrition", 4th ed., Academic Press, New York, 1997.
- E. N. Harshman, "Distribution of elements in some roll-type uranium deposit". IAEA, Vienna technical reports, 1974, 169-183.
- Khageshwar Singh Patel, Rajiv Mohan Verma and Rajendra Kumar Mishra, *Anal. Chem.*, 1982, **54**, 52.
- Z. Marczenko, "Spectrophotometric Determination of Elements", Harwood, Chichester, 1976, Ch. 32.
- P. K. Tarafder and A. K. Sardana, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 2000, **45**, 145.
- P. K. Tarafder, S. Durani, R. Saran and G. V. Ramnaiah, *Talanta*, 1994, **41**, 1345.
- R. K. Mondal and P. K. Tarafder, *Microchim. Acta*, 2004, **148**, 327.
- P. K. Tarafder, R. K. Mondal and S. Chattopadhyaya, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 2009, **54**, 231.
- V. Patrovsky, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1970, **35**, 1599.
- R. N. Soni and J. S. Nahata, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 446.
- P. K. Tarafder, R. K. Mondal, L. Kunkal, P. Murugan and D. P. S. Rathore, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 2004, **49**, 251.
- P. K. Tarafder, P. Murugan, L. Kunkal and D. P. S. Rathore, *J. Radioan. and Nucl. Chem.*, 2002, **253**, 135.
- P. K. Tarafder, S. K. Pradhan and R. K. Mondal (Unpublished work).
- T. Takayanagi and T. Yotsuyanagi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1994, **67**, 1835.
- P. K. Tarafder, S. K. Pradhan, R. K. Mondal and S. Roychoudhary (Unpublished work).
- A. Hrdlicka and M. Vrechlabsky, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1989, **11**, 55.
- P. C. H. Mitchell, *Rev. Q.*, 1966, **20**, 103.
- L. G. Sillen, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 185.
- R. Dass, J. K. Kapoor and S. Gambhir, *J. of Chem.*, Hindawi Publishing Corporation, 2013, Article ID. 420768, 6.
- E. L. Hendawy, A. M., W. P. Griffith, C. A. O'Mahoney and D. J. Williams, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 519.